

THE ROLE OF TRADITIONAL CRADLES (BESHIK) ON RISING CHILDREN

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi rivojlanayotgan bolalar uchun an'anaviy Osiyo beshigining rolini ko'rsatishdir, chunki u yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarni sovuqdan, ochiq olovdan yoki uy hayvonlaridan himoya qilish va boshqalar kabi turli maqsadlarga ega, ammo ba'zi tadqiqotchilar va shifokorlar beshik o'sayotgan bolalarga xavfli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. O'zbekistonning Farg'ona viloyatida yashovchi o'zbek onalar o'rtasida an'anaviy beshiklardan foydalanishda qanday afzallik va kamchiliklarga duch kelganliklarini tahlil qilish maqsadida so'rov o'tkazildi.

Kalit so'zlar: An'anaviy beshik, sog'liqni saqlash, belkurak, ota-ona va bola munosabatlari, bolaning psixologik faoliyati.

Abstract: This thesis aims to show the role of the traditional Asian cradle board (beshik) on rising children because of different goals, such as preventing new born babies from cold, open fires or domestic animals and others, however some researchers and doctors claim that beshik has a hazardous effects on rising children. Survey has been taken among uzbek mothers who live in Fergana region of Uzbekistan in order to analyze what kind of advantages and disadvantages they have faced, while using traditional cradles.

Keywords: Traditional cradle board, beshik, healthcare, swaddling, parent-child relationship, child's psychological functioning.

Аннотация: Цель данной работы показать роль традиционной азиатской колыбели для растущих детей, поскольку она преследует различные цели, такие как защита новорожденных от холода, открытого огня или домашних животных и другие, однако некоторые исследователи и врачи утверждают, что

колыбел оказывает опасное воздействие на растущих детей. Был проведен опрос среди узбекских матерей, проживающих в Ферганской области Узбекистана, с целью анализа того, с какими преимуществами и недостатками они столкнулись при использовании традиционных колыбелей.

Ключевые слова: Традиционная колыбельная доска, бешик, здравоохранение, пеленание, детско-родительские отношения, психологическое функционирование ребенка.

What should parents consider when raising children? In this section the work of other researchers and authors are provided to show the attitudes of experts towards the usage of beshik on growing infants. Child is precious blessing and the person who continues the lineage, hence first and foremost, it also related to their parents to make them healthy, intelligent and successful in the future. It is undeniable fact that, in this competitive and technological period, keen-witted youngsters govern the world. Over the last few decades have seen dramatic increase in rising children properly, as today's modern and educated mothers are making effort to collect sufficient data on childcare by reading and learning more about this realm, because every parent aspire their kids to make their dreams come true. This scientific article aims to give clear data on Central Asian cradleboards (beshik), because in some nations it is considered as crucial thing and new mothers received beshik as a gift when they give birth their first child

Traditional cradle (beshik) is very common in use amid uzbek families as well, but mothers do not know exactly what are the pros and cons of it to their infants. Jake Zawlacki and Matthew Derrick¹ state in their article that when kyrgyz mothers have been asked about how they learned this skill, majority of them said that they have

¹ Jake Zawlacki and Matthew Derrick. "The Persistence of traditional cradle board(beshik) usage among Post-soviet Central Asian Mothers: Survey analysis from Southeren Kyrgyzstan. Published: 8 October 2020

learned from elders and the people around them. It is clear that, there is strong influence of elders and surrounding on generations. In their article it is mentioned that even terrible cause has been observed because of cradle such as sudden death of infants and lung infection.

This scientific article portrays data on the reasons for using beshik among uzbek.

Research conducted by Lana B.Karasik² indicates that according to the prevailing view among pediatricians and psychologists, severe movement restriction in infancy could have deleterious effects, especially across the first two postnatal years, a critical period in children's health and development. Their research aims to learn deeply about gahvora (it is called like that in Tajikistan) with the help of tajik mothers and experts. Author said that: "The drapes limit exposure to sunlight, which may be a factor associated with vitamin D deficiency reported in this region."

Zakirjan Ibragimov³ said in his scientific article that: "A thousand-years-old tradition is putting the lives of uzbek babies at risk, warn doctors in Tashkent." It is not prohibited among inhabitants, because beshik shows the cultural identity of some countries. " A person who loves their child will never put him/her in a beshik, " said professor Rishat Osmonov, who heads the department for children's traumatology, orthopaedy and neurosurgery at the Andjan state medical institute. Myriad of researches show that the disadvantages of using traditional cradles outweigh advantages.

Materials and Methods

Quantitative survey research is the most common types of research in the field of healthcare and childcare. Here quantitative research is used to find out myriad of

² Lana.BKarasik, Catherine S.TamisLeMonda. The ties that bind: Cradling in Tajikistan. Published 2018 on October 31

³ Zakirjan Ibragimav. Uzbekistan: Cot Hazards Ignored. Published 21 february, 2005

details about the usage of beshik among uzbek families and the reasons why they are used while growing infants. In the questionnaire 200 mothers participated and the results are showed. Furthermore, in order to explore broad information about this sphere the work of other researchers has been learned as well and by relaying on secondary method and primary method is organized among uzbek mothers in order to comparing the results and reasons of using cradles among kyrgyz and tajik families according to the research of other authors. Here questions are showed that have been given to mothers

1. How have you learned cradling?
2. What kind of benefits are you taking by it to your infants?
3. Have you ever faced with harmful effects due to cradling?

As a Result Almost in each nation which traditional cradles are utilized has the same purpose from the usage of it. While learning the work of other authors that has been conducted among tajik and krgyz mothers, it became clear that uzbek mothers are somehow look like them as well. According to survey among 200 uzbek mothers, most of them said about disadvantages that have been observed in their children as well. 25% of mothers claimed that because of improper cradling, legs of their kids developed irregularly and other 55 % said that it was my big mistake that I did to my child due to my inexperience. Because lying on beshik during the long hours influenced to the back side of infants so that the head shaped improperly and came to ugly position. They feel stressed when their children complain about their head. Especially, for girls the fabulous shape of back side of head is important as hairstyles may not be well-matched in some cases. Fortunately, amid uzbek participators sudden death has not been observed during the usage of beshik, but 11% krgyz mothers said that they lost their babies due to fatal accidents by cradling(Jake

Zawlacki and Matthew Derricks) As a result of regular rocking of the cradle, the child’s head shakes and it is difficult for him/her to move because of bound limbs. Other 20% uzbek mothers have not witnessed any negative sides of beshik, because the body shape of their infants developed properly.

Discussion

To begin with, this discussion is framed around the conclusions of medical researchers, but only countable mothers receive the advice of specialists. Among the participators of Jake Zawlacki and matthew Derrick only 11.4 (55 of 481) received a doctor’s consultation about the beshik.“Thirty of the consultations explicitly advised against using the cradle board, yet only six participants reported complying with that recommendation”, said authors. It is clear that, some people do not want to confer about this field with doctors and prefer to do ongoing traditions that are

passing from their mothers. The movement of infants is rejected in beshik so that Rishat Osmonov said that: “A child’s development is in its movement, movement is life.” Not only traditional cradles influence the appearance of children, but also forcefully rocking a child in a beshik can effect cerebral haemorrhages, brain tumours and fractures to the fragile skull of an infant. Why mothers put their infants to beshik instead of spending more time and enjoying each minute of this contemporary childhood, also it is very low compared to maturity? There is one question that are other tasks such as career or household chores are important compared to the great blessing of life? Children need enough vitamins that provide their development, especially vitamin D that is taken from Sun. Lying on the dark beshik during the long hours without any movement had deleterious effects on developing language skills and beginning how to walking. Children should see the environment and learn anything by touching that they are interested and asking from parents. However, the usage of beshik can not be banned, because aforementioned factors promote that there are some positive sides of these cradles and each parents has promotion to decide for their children. For example, many uzbek families know the beshik as the inseparable part of their life. It is undeniable fact that estimating that 8 out of 10 uzbek children born today are vulnerable and sickly. Professor Osmonov believes that beshik’s main problem is that it immobilises the child. “ Additionally, children who are put in beshiks are more likely to develop abnormal hip bones and sacral bones’, said Osmonov. As a result of expertise on parents about how to rise children properly, children can rise without ant struggles on their bones or outfit, even though they are not tied to the cradles.

Conclusion

While tying to cradles can be convinient in some situations, it presents numerous disadvantages that should be carefully considered. Tying to cradles can limit

children's mobility and independence, especially when they are trying to move around or complete tasks. Additionally, it can be uncomfortable and restrictive, leading to physical discomfort and potential health issues. Therefore, alternative solutions that support freedom of movement and preserve autonomy should be explored to mitigate these disadvantages.

REFERENCE

1. Zakirjan Ibragimov. Uzbekistan: Cot Hazards Ignored. Published 21 february, 2005
2. Leonid M.Popov Ruth Ilesanmi, Kazan(Volga region) federal University. Online published: March 30,2015. E-mail:ruthilesanmi01@gmail.com. Parent-child relationship: Peculiarities and outcome
3. Lana.BKarasik, Catherine S.TamisLeMonda. The ties that bind: Cradling in Tajikistan. Published 2018 on October 31
4. Jake Zawlacki and Matthew Derrick. " The Persistence of traditional cradle board(beshik) usage among Post-soviet Central Asian Mothers: Survey analysis from Southern Kyrgyzstan..
5. Bettelheim, B. (1987). A Good Enough Parent. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.
6. Bowlby, J. (1961). Maternal Care and Mental Health. Geneva: World Health Organization